

Orality and Spelling Economy in Written Platform: An Analysis of the Facebookers' Comments

Syeda Asia Fatima^{a*}, Seemab Jamil Ghouri^b, Dr.Mudasar Jahan^c

^aLecturer at the University of Management and Technology, Sialkot. ^bLecturer at the University of Management and Technology, Sialkot. ^cEnglish Department, Hafiz Hayat Campus, University of Gujrat, ,Gujrat, Pakistan
^{*}**Email:** mudasar.jehan@uog.edu.pk

Abstract: This study investigates spelling economy and orality in Facebook language among undergraduates by utilizing the Grounded Theory of Glaser and Strauss (1969) and the categories created by Hamzah, Ghorbani, and Abdullah (2009). This study explores spelling economy and orality on Facebook's commentary boxes, contributing to understanding how language learners navigate spelling complexities in the digital realm. The study aims to fill a literature gap by examining the specific types of spelling errors commonly encountered by university-level students on Facebook. Three new spelling types have been added as contribution categories to the existing categories by Hamza et al. (2009). The study suggests that spelling errors have become a new invention as the spelling economy contains oral traits. Non-standard spellings on virtual social networking sites are not considered spelling errors but a new emerging internet language. The study suggests creating a model list based on a new spelling intervention to aid in understanding the new language on social media. This study, focusing on university-level students and Facebook as the analysis platform, has limitations, including potential biases in self-reported language proficiency.

Keywords: Spellings-Economy, Facebookers, Non-standard Spellings, Comments.

1. Introduction

This study explores the spelling economy and orality nuance in Facebook language using the Grounded theory, as per (Glaser and Strauss' 1969) framework. Hamza et al.'s (2009) study is taken as a sample for studying spelling patterns in Facebook comments, focusing on letter and digital homophones, improper abbreviations, punctuation errors, emoticons, and colloquialisms. The researcher's interest in the study was established to observe the increasing trend in the spelling economy on social media, especially in online communication platforms like Facebook. Users often employ various strategies to save time and effort while conveying their messages. For instance, they may use numerical digits like "2" instead of the word "to" or "too" or abbreviations like "u" instead of "you." Additionally, homophones are commonly used to achieve spelling economy, such as using "gr8" instead of "great." These examples illustrate how individuals adapt their spelling to fit the fast-paced nature of online interactions (Cook, 2013).

While spelling economy can enhance efficiency in online communication, it also poses specific

challenges. Improper use of abbreviations can sometimes lead to misunderstandings, as different individuals may interpret them differently. For example, the acronym "LOL" is commonly used to imply "laugh out loud," but how one interprets it depends on the situation and the person using it. Furthermore, excessive use of spelling shortcuts might hinder language ability, especially for those learning a second language. Striking a balance between spelling economy and maintaining clarity and accuracy in communication is crucial.

A recent trend of Facebook creations resembling the spelling economy is examined and categorised in this study. With 800 million active members, this social networking site (SNS) is well-known (Crystal, 2006). Barnes (2003) claims that Facebook provides spoken trends in written language. Communication on Facebook carries traits of orality (Boyd & Ellison, 2007). This article explores the emerging trend of the spelling economy on Facebook. A sample population of one hundred snap-shots was selected from the commentary boxes to consummate it for content analysis. As a theoretical approach, the Grounded Theory developed by Glaser and Strauss in 1969 has been applied. Grounded Theory is a theoretical lens that is accomplished by classifying data. The selected data is enumerated into categories designed by Hamza et al. (2009) to accentuate Grounded Theory.

2. Review of the Literature

Academic language focuses on standard language and spelling, while social media language produces a new spelling trend. On SNSs, non-standard spellings substitute the common spellings (Dąbrowska, 2018). Internet users have introduced innovative ways to express themselves in net language, which is dynamic and multidimensional (Lee, 2007). New spelling inventions have been used in the English age and all languages worldwide (Crystal, 2006). Apart from the conventional techniques of writing and creating acronyms, like ASAP (as soon as possible) and BTW (by the way), there are other novel approaches available for making acronyms on the internet. Homophones U (you), R (are), and the most recent ones, LOL (laughing out loud), BRB (be right back), and GTG (got to go) are examples of acronyms (Werry, 1996; Crystal, 2001).

Bodomo (2009) gives some spelling variations on the internet. Tastan (2012) discusses spellings regarding homophony and shortening of words invented on Twitter. Hamzah et al. (2009) briefly divided text on cell phone messaging and found three typing changes: letter homophony, digital homophony, and improper use of abbreviations. Symbolic homophony is discovered by Lee (2007) on the internet.

Certain elements are exclusive to spellings, including emoticons (smiley faces) and acronyms (FAQ, WTF, IMHO, LOL). Kate (2007) investigates different letters, numbers, and symbols on social networking sites that carry the same sound but a different script than the standard, which does not exist in any dictionary. Instead, it is a Netspeak or social media language known as homophony. According to Lee (2007), the technique of changing the digits or integers to mimic the target word, such as for too / to /2, and for / 4, is called digital homophony, and these words prevalently exist on the internet is called digital homophony. The example of the most used type of letter homophone on Facebook is 'U' for you and t for 'tea' (Berasa & Mous, 2009). According to Lee (2007), it was discovered that throughout the talks, the copular verb "is" was abbreviated to "R". Nonetheless, a number of ways to arbitrarily shorten "are" were discovered in Facebook communications. A novel kind of homophony has been discovered on the corpus of social networking sites, distinct from homophony involving numbers and letters.

This dynamic and revolutionary homophony with newness and novelty is known as symbolic homophony. Some typographical symbols, i.e. @ /at the rate of/ and mathematical characters as '+' to show something (Lee, 2007). Improper Abbreviations/Acronyms or Shortening is also in vogue. An acronym is, by definition, a word that has been shortened by using the initials of several words spoken together as a single unit. Writing the language in shortened forms or abbreviations has been a prominent and common feature of CMC since its beginning. Thurlow (2018) asserts that young texters are reshaping language through the creation of new words and spellings. Crystal (2006) said that one of the mentioned linguistic features of CMC is the novel use of shortenings and abbreviations, unlike fixed abbreviations and initializations. Computer-mediated communication has its typology for writing words in brevity (Lee, 2002). He adds (2007) that the time-saving or language economy method is now

part and parcel of Facebook language. Thurlow (2018) anticipated the maxim of shortness on Facebook texting, manifested in the abbreviation of lexical items. Elvis (2009) noted that initializations, acronyms, and the removal of vowels are a few strategies used to condense words.

In contrast to the traditional categorization of acronyms, Facebook shortenings are no longer limited to acronyms and cross-cultural initialisms. A few of them may be more "universal" or pervasive. Some of the acronyms are quite context-specific, so people who are not familiar with them might not understand them. Lee (2007) found that five types of new shortenings or abbreviations are observed on Facebook: BTW or btw "by the way" and b4 (before), U (You), ASAP (as soon as possible), and bcoz (because). And af Hård Segerstad (2005) also elicited some abbreviations such as (CU) for see you or (BB) for bye-bye, Talk to you later (TTUL / TTUL8R). In comparison to ad-hoc abbreviations like abt, den, Fri, gd, ltr, msg, tis, and tat, more instances of the more popular and conventional abbreviations like btw, pleas / plz, andur were observed. Shortenings like (np) for no problem, (msg) for message, and (mb) for maybe are examples of Lee's (2007) shortenings. Other examples include the reduction of sound segments, such as (LING) for Linguistics and (Soci) for Sociology.

Shortenings are unique to Facebook, even if the majority of terms on the platform are common expressions. Hale and Scanlon (1999) presented a list of abbreviations used in net language. Punctuation Errors are also in use on the internet. Punctuation marks are used as signals to the reader. We can pause, stop, or change our voice when a person speaks. We need to signal how we want them to read our writing when we write. According to af Hård Segerstad (2005), punctuation is used in written language to distinguish between grammatical units such as sentences, clauses, phrases, and words. It's amazing to see how people who communicate online have evolved their punctuation styles. There seem to be no 'rules' for punctuation in Computer-Mediated Communication.

Non-standard punctuation may serve linguistic functions: There are capital errors, emoticons, and colloquialisms in text messaging Hamzah et al. (2009). Punctuation error marks of exclamation are frequent on social media (Elvis, 2009). Question marks, omission of apostrophes, and commas are frequently observed on Facebook (af Hård Segerstad, 2005). Capital errors are frequent in the language of social media (Ling, 2005). Thurlow and Poff (2011) said emoticons are frequent on social media. af Hård Segerstad (2005) and David (1993) claimed colloquialism on social media. Pearson, Nelson, Titsworth, and Harter (2017) observed ellipses, irregular punctuation marks on Facebook, and all other irregularities found on the internet. Ellipses are punctuation marks observed prevalently on Facebook that must be looked at. Mark of Exclamation (!) is also used in a new way on the internet.

The exclamation mark is used at the end of a sentence or after an interjection to show strong emotion or emphasis. Exclamation points are one instance of non-standard punctuation usage. It is not used conservatively but in a rather impetuous and off-the-cuff manner. Exclamation points are frequently used in computer-mediated communication to highlight the tone of speech and convey the encoder's zeal for the online medium (Elvis, 2009). Question Marks????: Many question marks are used at the end of questions. This includes incomplete questions and statements intended as questions. On the internet, question marks are also not utilized in a traditional way, but rather haphazardly and spontaneously. Marks provide yet another instance of non-standard punctuation usage. They are applied in the subsequent manners: use of question marks repeatedly to show that the message writer is inquisitive and ready to learn the truth; mixture of? And! (?! or!?): to convey both astonishment and scepticism at the same time (af Hård Segerstad, 2005).

Omission of the Apostrophe (') / Period (.) Comma (,): Apostrophe is used with nouns to show possession. To indicate that the statement has been completed, full stops or periods are used at the end of sentences. Commas can show the reader how extra information has been added to a sentence. In electronic discourse, non-alphabetic characters such as apostrophes, commas, and periods are mostly omitted by participants. This saves time and space (af Hård Segerstad, 2005). Thurlow and Poff (2011) investigate the omission of non-alphabetic characters in electronic discourse and state that fluency in thoughts and informal writing causes people to be careless, which leads to the omission of apostrophes, periods, and commas.

Capital letter Errors are part of Netspeak. Ling (2005) elaborates that capitalizing the first letter is

custom, and it appears none accepted on the internet. Language is written smoothly in small letters, which are shortened than the original words. Thurlow and Poff (2011) theorized that the omission of capital letters is due to the overall fluidity of interaction. As people write what they think, they do not care for linguistic implications on SM, which is the interaction source for the everyday person worldwide. On the Internet, emoticons are drawings that serve as a substitute for spoken gestures. We have been able to communicate with people online from the early days of computer-mediated communication, such as emails, where written words are used primarily to convey messages (Park et al., 2014). However, because the term only conveys the actual meaning of the utterances in face-to-face communication, it is merely an indirect component of the entire message. Written words are unable to convey certain linguistic or paralinguistic components that are essential to understanding a message, such as tones, gestures, and facial expressions. Consequently, it is possible for a written communication to have errors that cause the recipient to interpret the sender's intended message differently. Internet users must therefore make up for the lost content by using the computer's keyboard to its fullest extent as a means of communication. Online communicators began representing non-literal meanings, including emotions and attitudes, with non-alphabet buttons like numerals, punctuations, and other symbols found on a computer keyboard. The depiction consists primarily of a straightforward icon that combines two or three non-alphabet elements. Typically, icons convey the interlocutors' feelings. The most well-known icon in the conversations is the smiley face :) ; people have dubbed this expression "Emoticons" or "Smileys." Emotional content on social media is ideal for in-person interactions (Nguyen & Le, 2022).

As for coordinating with the change of the communication mode, the interlocutors tend to shift their conversation to the face-to-face end as well. af Hård Segerstad (2005) says that the use of emoticons in today's Facebook communication is not only due to the compensation of missing meaning of the message but also aims to deliver a more accurate and finer non-literal meaning that is expressed in the spoken face-to-face communication.

To convey a more sensitive facial emotion, one approach is to embellish the emoticons using English letters. The majority of participants utilize emoticons like wink (~_^), sad (-_-), and smile (^_^). As a result, it takes less time and effort to insert non-alphabetic symbols like (:), (-), and (:). (af Hård Segerstad, 2005). A list of smileys was provided by Sanderson (1993): Basic Smileys: :-), amusement, enjoyment, :-), melancholy, discontent :-), winking (in any sense) ;-(sobbing %-(-, %-) bewildered:-0, shocked:-0, amazed:-),-[caustic Funny Smileys [-:-)The person has on a Walkman. 8-) The user has on sunglasses. B: The person has sunglasses on their head:-{ The user has a facial hair. User is intoxicated:-] The user is a vampire (E) The user is a vampire with buckteeths-F The user is a vampire with buck teeth and one missing tooth. The user is yelling and has a cold. The user is punk. -:-(Sincere punks never smile +-: - User works in a Christian ministry. Zero:-) The user is fundamentally an angel. Stories about smileys:-) 8-) 8-}) A smiley gets spectacles and a fake moustache to hide themselves. C: -) > [] C8-) A cunning griny went.

Colloquialism is close to the internet: Elements of colloquialism are mostly culture-oriented and are usually found in spoken language. These are colloquial terms that people in a community who share a similar culture often understand (Pearson et al., 2017). Later penetrated CMC and social media are not away from accepting this technique. However, on social media, this technique is not culture-restricted; instead, it has characteristics of a universal nature According to Ling's (2005) findings, teenagers were more likely than older users to text others on Facebook using their universal languages.

As far as conventions of spelling and punctuation marks are concerned, irregularities found by Hamzah et al. (2009), specifically on text messaging, and irregularities found by Elvis (2009), af Hård Segerstad (2005), Ling (2005), Thurlow, C. (2018), Pearson et al. (2008) on the internet has been studied on Facebook writing. It is found that internet and text messaging irregularities are present on social media profoundly, along with some new conventions. A new type of homophony by the name of alphanumeric homophony prevalently exists on Facebook, and a type of punctuation mark (ellipsis) is found abundantly in a non-standard and irregular way, but it is not studied yet; it needs to be studied.

The study aims to find out the spelling invention on Facebook wall. The research questions are: What types of spellings, economy, and orality exist on Facebook's commentary boxes? Grounded theory (GT),

a research method, has been used as a theoretical framework. Hamzah et al. (2009) sample categories tabulate the data and sort out the research problems. The study's significance lies in the fresh viewpoint it will provide on spelling innovations with oral qualities in written communication.

3. Methodology

This is a qualitative study based on one hundred sample sentences selected randomly from the commentary boxes. The nature of the study is the constructivism paradigm. The research concerns are examined within the theoretical framework of Grounded Theory (GT), as developed by Glasser and Strauss in 1969. Creating or discovering a new theory from the data collected is the main goal of the theory's study design. GT theory is objective and is used to solve problems where existing theories do not help investigate research problems (Borgatti & Ofem, 2010). GT is also problem-solving-oriented instead of hypothesis-oriented. This study designs a model for spelling economy types with a nuance of orality.

Table 1: Phases in Grounded Theory (Glasser & Strauss, 1969)

PHASE	→	STEPS
Initial or open coding=text	→	Categories: Properties line by line and word by word
Focused or selective coding, category development=code	→	Selective coding: Begins when a core category has been found.
Axial or thematic coding, sorting=subcategories	→	Sorting database: Memos showing the emergence of theories
Write up=categories	→	Communicable: A form of theory

Table 2: Categories on Economy of language (Hamzah et al., 2009)

Categories	Description
Letter Homophones	single letters are used to stand in for homophones or similar-sounding words, such as R, C, U, B, and Y.
Digital Homophones	The representation of words that sound alike with numbers, such as 2, 4, 8
Improper Use of Abbreviations	Any condensed form of a word or phrase is referred to as an acronym. Words, acronyms, and initialisms can be replaced with traditional and ad hoc abbreviations, such as abt, asap, bro, btw, cs /cz/cos, and so on.
Punctuation Errors	Incorrect punctuation, such as omitting an apostrophe, using... or using???

Capital Errors The deletion of capitalization for the initial word of a sentence, proper nouns

and, when necessary.

Emoticons The electromagnetic transmission of emotions to another individual through symbols, such as 3

Colloquialism The utilization of regionally specific formal phrases, such as la, bha, and erect

To find the answer to the research problem, what types of spellings, economy, and orality exist on Facebook's commentary boxes? A sample of a hundred Facebook users/students has been classified into Hamzah et al. (2009) categories. The researcher adds categories other than those of Hamzah et al. (2009) to fill the research gap in the reign of the spelling economy.

4. Results

For content analysis, the spelling economy and orality scores for one hundred chosen comments are chosen without regard to gender.

4.1 Examples of Spellings Economy and Orality

Social networking sites are now part and parcel of a student's life. They keep socializing inside and outside the school, college, and university. Having an informal and chatty atmosphere, most do not care for the spelling and punctuation limitations. They have to write instantly, just like in face-to-face communication. So, to save time and spontaneous flow of ideas, misspell the words and do not care for the punctuation errors. Categories made by Hamzah et al. (2009) for cell phone text messaging have been applied to determine the deviations from standard spellings on Facebook language.

4.1.1 Homophony

The first and foremost observed digital writing device found on Facebook is homophony. Homophony is a condition where a word is replaced with a letter, digit, or a mixture of letter and word and with some symbol.

4.1.1.1 Digital Homophony

Example.1: Any 14rm BS7thsem?

Translation: Anyone from BS 7th semester?

Example.2: gud2 c u

Translation: Good to see you.

In the examples given above, the word "one" has been replaced with the digit "1," and in the second sentence word "two" has been replaced with the digit "2". When the questionnaire was distributed among students, 80% said they used letters instead of complete words while writing on Facebook. This idea matches with the research of Lee (2007) on the internet. He said that in the convention of internet language, people have started using digits instead of writing the whole word.

4.1.1.2 Letter Homophony

Example.1: All uni bloks r beautiful

Translation: All University blocks are beautiful

Example.2: Enjoyed 2dy t__prty

Translation: Enjoyed today tea party

In the above examples, the word 'are' has been substituted with the letter 'r' and the word 'tea' with 't'. This idea matches the research of (Berasa & Mous, 2009) and Lee (2007). They said that people on social media think and write simultaneously, so due to limited time, they write words that carry phonetically the same sounds.

4.1.1.3 Alphanumeric Homophony

Example.1: Dear 4ndz. Kindly semester freeze karwane ky bary me kici ko info hai toh rep Karen, .semester freeze karwane ki conditions etc.....Plzzzzzz rep its urgent

Translation: Dear friends, if somebody have information about, how to freez semester and its conditions please let me know.

Example.2: Struggle 4r success makes u master and struggle 4r satisfaction makes u legend. Good night.

Translation: Struggle for success makes you master, and struggle for satisfaction makes you a legend. Goodnight.

In the above examples, the word 'for' is substituted with '4r' and 'friends' with '4ndz'. Alphanumeric is a new homophony type not discussed by Hamzah et al. (2012). Alphanumeric is an addition to the existing table of abbreviations for SNS conversations.

4.1.1.4 Symbolic Homophony

Example. 1: @ linguists 7th semster, result 'll b disply 2marow

Translation: This is news for Linguistics 7th semester, the result will be displayed tomorrow.

Example. 2: boys ±girls wr invited to the prty.

Translation: Boys and girls were invited in the party.

In the above examples, @ has been used to address somebody. @ "stands for at the rate of." Furthermore, + for showing "both." Symbolic Homophony coincides with the research of (Lee, 2007). He said that a novel trait of Netspeak has come in vogue, a usually mathematical symbol that replaces a word or a phrase.

4.1.2 Improper Abbreviations/Acronyms or Shortening

Any word that has been abbreviated from an acronym or word made up of the initial letter or letters of a string of words is an acronym: laser (light amplification by stimulated emission of radiation).

Example 1

Aoa.....! Bro agr date 30tk extend ho gai hy. Thn 1st merit list 4 ko he lgy ge????????? Haveu any idea.....????????????????????????????????

Translation: Aoa! Brother, if the date has been extended till the 30th, the list is expected to be displayed on the 4th. Do you have any idea?

Example 2

Asslamualaikum nd gud mOrning Pakistan. Toaba □ girls ka tou uog buses mein murgion kitarh hashar ho raha hota hai □ lol

Translation: Asslamualaikum and good morning, Pakistan. Hilarious! In the buses girls seems like hens :-) Laughter.

The use of the improper abbreviation is shared on Facebook; as mentioned in the above examples, the word 'brother' has been replaced with 'bro,' and 'lots of laughs,' a phrase that is replaced with 'lol.' Similarly, 'and' is replaced with 'n' and sometimes with 'nd.' All these characteristics match with the research of Crystal (2001); He claimed that, in contrast to set abbreviations, one of the linguistic elements of CMC that is worth emphasizing is the creative use of shortenings and abbreviations. af Hård Segerstad (2005) enlisted many words that carry the characteristic of shortening but new.

4.1.3 Punctuation Errors on Facebook

Some of the standard punctuation error observed on Facebook is given below.

Translation: When is the merit list going to be displayed?

In the above examples, too many question marks have been used. af Hård Segerstad (2005) said that in Netspeak, people usually put too many question marks between the sentences and at the end of the sentence to emphasize the text to highlight it.

4.1.3.4 Omission of the Apostrophe (s')/Period (.)Comma (,)

Apostrophes are used to show possession and to form contractions. Apostrophes are used to indicate letters missing from words and to create possessive forms of nouns. At the end of the sentence, punctuation lets the reader know when a thought is finished, known as a period or full stop. Commas are applied to separate the clauses of a sentence. They tell readers to pause between words, and they can clarify the meanings of sentences.

Example: Plz must watch n listen to it now may be it can change ur life Jap her roz itni movies n songs n other videos etc etc dekhty hn aj b dekhny zraa for success in ur life maybe is ka bht acha impression pary apki life py ho sakta apki life change ho jay isi sy its a "life- changing item, cha lgyya koi impression pty kisi pa tou wo mujy btaa zrur dy JJ is link par click kren just.

Paragraph with complete comma, periods and apostrophes

Plz must watch **and** listen it now, **may** be it can change **your** life. **Ap** her roz itni movies **and** songs **and** other videos etc dekhty hn, aj b dekhny zraa for success in your life. **May** be is ka bht acha impression pary apki life py. **Ho** sakta apki life change ho jay isi sy. It's a "life changing item, acha lgy ya koi impression pty kisi pa tou wo mujy btaa zrur dy
□□. Is link par click kren just□.

Translation: Please watch and listen to it now; it can bring revolutionary changes. You watch different movies and songs daily. Please watch this one as well to get success in your life. It may bring a good impression and change in your life. It is a life-changing item. If you like it or get some impression, please let me know; please click on the link :-)

In the above paragraph, apostrophes, periods, and commas have yet to be carefully considered. af Hård Segerstad's (2005) research work is also in the same line. He, too, said that people are not very careful about apostrophes, commas, and periods while writing on the Internet.

4.1.3.5 Capital Errors

The beginnings of phrases, direct quotations, and direct queries at the beginning of titles and subtitles are all capitalized; most adjectives for proper nouns are derived from proper nouns.

Example.1: Plz tell me **nat** test k marks ya percentile aggregate kya hota ha **Translation:** Please tell what difference between NTS percentile and aggregate is.**Example.2:** **M.phil** ke departmental tests kb ho rhay hn?? anybody tell me....

Translation: When is M.Phil. admission going to start, can anybody tell me?

In the abovementioned examples, the writers have ignored all proper nouns, which matches the research conducted by Thurlow and Poff (2011). They said that the omission of capital letters is due to the overall fluidity of social interaction. People write what they think, so they do not care about linguistic implications on social media, especially Facebook

4.1.4 Emoticons

Emoticons are collections of symbols that are used in text-based communication to reflect body language. It has been suggested that emoticons are artificial language constructs (Ptaszynski and Rzepka, 2011). They contended that emoticons have developed into an essential tool for text-based message support during the course of the more than 40 years that text-based communication has existed. They so fully belong to Natural Language Processing (NLP) as opposed to Unnatural Language Processing (UNLP).

Example 1

Party in 33 no buss.....-* thanx chachu gulzar such a lovely evening <3 <3<3 enjoyed a lot

;0) chachu g u r great.....:-*

Translation: It was a party on bus number 33. It was a lovely evening. <3 <3 >3.Thanks to Uncle Gulzar, you are great.

Example 2

Toaba☐ girls ka tou uog buses mein murgion ki tarh hasher ho raha hota hai☐lol

Translation: Uff! girls in buses seems like hens ☐ lol.

In the above examples, users have used different emoticons or similes to express their emotions, just like in spoken language. Research confines with the existing research of Hård Segerstad (2005). According to him, emoticons are designed to convey a nonliteral meaning in spoken face-to-face contact that is more precise and nuanced. To depict a more subtle facial expression, one approach is to embellish the emoticons using English letters.

4.1.5 Colloquialism

Example 1

Aj to cnten pi 4hr **avin** fazol gazar diya!!!! **Translation:**

Today we wasted four hours at canteen!**Example 2**

Oay hero lukiing kool yara!

Translation: Hy, hero you are looking cool.

In the above examples, words like ‘avian’ and ‘oay’ are colloquial words and part of the local dialect in Punjab. This characteristic is like the research results (Pearson et al., 2017). He said that people use culturally oriented colloquial words in their speech.

4.2 Discussion

Facebook language is a new genre aligning with Barnes' 2003 hypothesis, suggesting the development of Computer-Mediated Communication is imminent. Crystal (2006) highlights internet language as a hybrid of traditional speech and writing, Engrossing national languages and local vernacular with English to enable people to communicate feelings and conciseness.

Facebook shares similarities with spoken language, bridging spoken and written communication allowing people to share views and opinions on single posts. Facebook incorporates Romanization techniques to incorporate both languages, resulting in a conversational, chatty tone with distinct phonological sounds. Facebook users engage in conversational and socialization through its unique spelling economy, preferring to write in shortened and abbreviated forms with punctuation variations. Facebook's unique feature is its synchronic and asynchronous ability, allowing users to converse on posted statuses simultaneously or when logged in to their account. The study identifies new features, such as digital letter homophony, ellipses, and transliteration, in the Facebook language, based on categories designed by Hamzah et al. (2009) for SMS.

Though not academically and universally accepted, these precise items carry much wattage in the SM / Facebook language domain. The obtained results match James (2001), who states that the study reveals that Hong Kong students heavily use abbreviations, smileys, using emoticons in their emails to communicate the modal and attitudinal content of conversations, even though they are not universally accepted. The study reveals that spelling and punctuation variations enhance orality and prosodic effects, while intonations enhance language comprehensibility for readers. Facebook language's emoticons make it easier to understand than academic language, as it requires deep insight for discourse analysis. Table 3 presents a list of uniqueness categories, including three additions from Hamza et al. (2009), specifically for spelling types on social media.

Table 3: Accumulative Results of Facebook Language (Orality & Economy of spellings).

Spelling variation	Alphanumeric homophony
Punctuation variation	Ellipses (.....)

research on the social media platform.

References

- Barnes, S. B. (2003). Computer-mediated communication: human-to-human communication across the Internet. *Boston (Mass): Allyn and Bacon*.
- Berasa, S., & Mous, M. (2009). The Oral and Written Interface in SMS: Technologically Mediated Communication in Kenya. Netherland: LOT.
- Bodomo, A.B. (2009). Computer-mediated Communication for Linguistics and Literacy: Technology and Natural Language Education. *University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong. Hershey: IGI Global*.
- Borgatti, S. P., & Ofem, B. (2010). Overview: Social network theory and analysis. In A. J. Daly (Ed.), *The ties of change: Social network theory and application in education*. (pp. 17-30). Cambridge, MA: Harvard Press. Pdf.
- Boyd, D. M., & Ellison, N. B. (2007). Social Network Sites: Definition, History, and Scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13 (1), 210–230. Borgatti, S., ND. Introduction to Grounded Theory,
- V. (2013). The language of the street. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 4(1), 43–81. Crystal, D. (2001). *Language and Internet*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Crystal, D. (2006). *Language and the Internet* (2nd ed.). New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Dąbrowska, M. (2018). Abbreviated English—A typical feature of online communication? *Studia Linguistica Universitatis Jagellonicae Cracoviensis*, 135(4), 235-251.
- David, S. (1993). *Smileys, O'Reilly and Associates in David Crystal language and internet*, Cambridge University Press.
- Elvis, F. W. (2009). The Sociolinguistics of Mobile Phone SMS Usage in Cameroon and Nigeria. *The International Journal of Language Society and Culture*, p. 28.
- Glaser, B.G., & Strauss, A.L. (1969). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research* New York: Aldine de Gruyter.
- Hale, C., & Scanlon, J. (1999). *Wired Style: Principles of English Usage in the Digital Age*. New York: Broadway Books.
- Hamzah, M., Ghorbani, M., & Abdullah, S. K. B. (2009). The Impact of Electronic Communication Technology on Written Language. *Online Submission*, 6(11), 75-79.
- James, J. D. (2001). The role of cognitive development and socialisation in the initial development of team loyalty. *Leisure Sciences*, 23(4), 233–261.
- Lee, C. (2002). Telecommunications Reforms in Malaysia. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*. 73, pp. 521–540.
- Lee, K. M. C. (2007). Linguistic features of email and ICQ instant messaging in Hong Kong. In B. Danet & S. C. Herring (Eds.), *The multilingual internet: Language, culture, and communication online*. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press. pp. 184-208.
- Ling, R. (2005). The Socio-linguistics of SMS: An Analysis of SMS Use by a Random Sample of Norwegians. In R. Ling & Pedersen (Eds.) *Mobile Communications: Re- negotiation of the Social Sphere*. (pp 335–349) London: Springer. Retrieved January 30.
- Kate, R. (2007). Teachers Say Text Messages R Ruining Kids' Writing Skills. Retrieved February 27, 2011 from <http://findarticles.com/p/articles/mi-qa5369/is-200711/ai-n21298339/>.
- Nguyen, M. V., & Le, H. H. (2022, February). Mutual Effect Between Language Use and Media Technology via Digital Communication. In *International Conference on Science, Engineering Management and Information Technology* (pp. 261–278). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Park, J., Baek, Y. M., & Cha, M. (2014). Cross-cultural comparison of nonverbal cues in emoticons on Twitter: Evidence from extensive data analysis. *Journal of Communication*, 64(2), 333-354.
- Pearson, J. C., Nelson, P. E., Titsworth, S., & Harter, L. (2017). *Human communication* (p. 416). New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Ptaszynski, M., Rzepka, R., Araki, K., & Momouchi, Y. (2011). Research on emoticons: a review of the

field and proposal of research framework. *Proceedings of 17th Association for Natural Language Processing*, 1159-1162.

Sanderson, D. (1993). Smileys. Sebastopol, Ca: O'Reilly.

af Hård Segerstad, Y. (2005). Language in SMS—a socio-linguistic view. In *The inside text: Social, cultural and design perspectives on SMS* (pp. 33-51). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.

Thurlow, C. & Poff, M (2011). Text Messaging, *Handbook of the Pragmatics of CMC*. Berlin & New York: Mouton de Gruyters.

Thurlow, C. (2018). Digital discourse: Locating language in new/social media. *The SAGE handbook of social media*, pp. 135–145.